

Original Research

Do Foreign Equity ETFs Provide Diversification Benefits for South African Investors Under Bull and Bear Markets?

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Abstract

In recent years, financial markets have been plagued with heightened levels of volatility due to the COVID-19 pandemic, banking crises, inflation and interest rate upswings, fintech disruptions, and geopolitical tensions such as the Russia-Ukraine war, among other factors. Given the unanticipated rise in investment risk and uncertainty, investors seek alternative assets to diversify their portfolios and mitigate risk vulnerabilities. Recently, the popularity of exchange-traded funds (ETFs) has soared, with foreign equity ETFs providing easily accessible and low-cost exposure to international stock markets. On this background, this study aims to investigate whether foreign equity ETFs offer diversification benefits to South African investors under bull and bear markets. To achieve this objective, a modified version of the international capital asset pricing model (ICAPM) is employed with a Markov Regime-Switching framework to assess a sample of foreign-equity ETFs listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE). The findings of this study suggest that foreign equity ETFs do not serve as effective diversification tools for South African investors under both bullish and bearish market conditions because local market conditions compromise their diversification capabilities. This study explores the diversification benefits of foreign equity ETFs under varying market conditions, offering valuable insights for investors trading in these instruments, fund managers overseeing such portfolios, and regulators responsible for governing the ETF segment.

Keywords: Diversification, Exchange Traded Fund, International Capital Asset Pricing Model, Johannesburg Stock Exchange, Markov Regime-Switching.

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Introduction

Volatility is an essential phenomenon in financial markets and the world of finance. Engle (2004) defines volatility as the likelihood of a market experiencing significant short-term price movements at any given time. Patra (2024) highlights that those periods of increased risks, such as the global financial crisis of 2008 and the COVID-19 pandemic, are associated with highly volatile asset prices, leading to significant gains or losses. In recent years, international financial markets have experienced heightened volatility due to the COVID-19 pandemic, banking crises, inflationary pressures, rising interest rates, fintech disruptions, and geopolitical tensions. In response to such risks, financial theory has long emphasized diversification to manage uncertainty. Kritzman (2015) explains that diversification is a risk management strategy that combines various investments within a portfolio to reduce exposure to any single asset or risk. Given the unpredictable nature of markets, diversification across assets or sectors that do not share common risk exposures is considered essential for investors seeking to minimize portfolio volatility. Therefore, the objective of diversification is to offset losses in one asset class with gains in another, thereby stabilizing returns. In this context, Exchange Traded Funds (ETFs) have gained popularity as effective instruments for achieving diversification (Thanakijombat and Kongtoranin, 2018).

An Exchange-Traded Fund (ETF) is a pooled investment vehicle comprising a basket of securities designed to replicate the performance of a specific benchmark or index (Kunjai, et al., 2022). Unlike mutual funds² which can only be traded at the end of the trading day, ETFs offer continuous trading throughout market hours (Ben-David, et al., 2017). While ETFs share some features with mutual funds, such as a market value that closely tracks their net asset value (NAV), they provide several distinct advantages, including lower fees, intraday liquidity, transparency, and tax efficiency (Huang & Lin, 2011; Popa, 2017). Globally, the ETF market has grown significantly from one EFT in 1993 to over 1,000 ETFs in 2002 and by December of 2022, there were 8 522 ETF schemes worldwide (Joshi and Dash, 2024). This rapid growth is largely driven by increasing investor demand for diversified, low-cost investment options. ETFs offer exposure to various asset classes, investment strategies, and international markets, making them attractive tools for diversification. However, Miralles-Quirós, et al., (2019) highlight that the benefits of ETFs are best realized when they align with an investor's objectives, risk tolerance, and investment horizon.

International or foreign ETFs, which track offshore benchmarks, aim to offer diversification by providing access to global markets (Converse, Levy-Yeyati and Williams, 2023). However, their diversification potential can be limited by sensitivity to domestic market conditions (Thanakijombat & Kongtoranin, 2018). This sensitivity may vary depending on the prevailing market environment, making it important to investigate whether foreign equity ETFs can serve as reliable diversification tools during stable and volatile market phases. Accordingly, this study evaluates the extent to which foreign equity ETFs provide diversification benefits under bull and bear markets, such as periods of heightened uncertainty or relative calm. By distinguishing between these regimes, the

² A mutual fund is a type of investment vehicle where the money collected from various investors is pooled together to invest in different assets including bonds, stocks, and/or money market investments.

study contributes to a deeper understanding of the time-varying nature of ETF performance and its role in risk management.

The motivation for this study arises from the rapid growth of the international ETF market, which has become a significant innovation in the asset management industry over the past two decades (Filippou, et al., 2024). Reflecting this trend, South Africa has also seen a notable expansion in its ETF market, with the number of ETFs listed on the JSE increasing by 35% between 2019 and 2024. This growth has been further supported by the rise of active ETFs, which are projected to represent a larger share of total fund assets in the coming years (Kamil, et al., 2024). While South Africa has rich natural resources, a diverse economy, and a well-developed financial sector, it remains an emerging market vulnerable to persistent economic and political risks (Molele and Mukuddem-Petersen, 2020). Accordingly, May and Farrell (2018) mention that the South African rand (ZAR) is one of the most volatile emerging market currencies, often reacting sharply to global shocks, investor sentiment shifts, and domestic political developments. The high volatility in South Africa is mainly driven by global market volatility, commodity price volatility, and domestic political uncertainty (Chinzara, 2011). Given these challenges, this study investigates explicitly whether foreign ETFs can reduce local market risk exposure by offering diversification benefits that remain effective even in periods marked by ZAR volatility, geopolitical tensions, or macroeconomic stress.

In this approach, the study also seeks to determine whether the diversification capabilities of foreign ETFs vary across different market regimes, reflecting the principles of the Adaptive Market Hypothesis, which asserts that asset return dynamics change over time in response to evolving investor behaviour and market conditions (Lo, 2004). Furthermore, this study provides empirical evidence from an emerging market context, where volatility is more pronounced and diversification is more critical for portfolio risk reduction. Unlike most existing studies focusing on developed markets, this research is centred on South African-listed international ETFs, offering context-specific insights for local investors, fund managers, and policymakers.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: The next section reviews the relevant literature. An outline of the data and methodology follows this. Thereafter, the empirical findings are discussed. The final section concludes the study and highlights its implications.

Literature Review

Theoretical Review

In 2004, Lo developed the Adaptive Market Hypothesis theory, which combines the popular, controversial Efficient Market Hypothesis and behavioural finance theories. The A.M.H. asserts that investors are rational but tend to overreact during increased market volatility, opening up buying opportunities. In pursuit of this theory, Lo (2004) discovered that evolutionary models of human behaviour, such as competition, natural selection and adaptation, are consistent with investor behaviour such as loss aversion, overconfidence and overreaction. Urquhart and McGroarty (2016) mention that the A.M.H is off the view that investors learn from their mistakes and make predictions on

the future based on experience, as such Ghazani and Araghi (2014) further state that investors use trial and error method that is, if the investment strategy fails, investors are likely to take another strategy next time and if the strategy succeed, they are likely to try it again. Furthermore, the A.M.H acknowledges the time-varying fluctuations in financial markets due to microeconomics and macroeconomics factors (Dhankar & Shankar, 2016). Therefore, the A.M.H. demonstrates how the changes in market conditions can completely change the behaviour of investors and individuals.

Developed by Harry Markowitz (1952 and 1959), the modern portfolio theory (MPT) asserts that investors are risk-averse; for a given level of expected return, investors will always prefer the less risky portfolio (Curtis, 2004). The modern portfolio theory follows an assumption that a stock is evaluated not just in isolation but also in relation to the rest of the portfolio and whether adding it would increase portfolio return without increasing risk (Rani, 2012). Additionally, the M.P.T seeks to reduce portfolio volatility without sacrificing returns by combining assets with low and negative correlations, and these assets have to possess different risk-return profiles, thus emphasizing the concept of diversification. As such, diversification in this theory is used as a portfolio allocation strategy to reduce the return change influenced by idiosyncratic risk by using the negative correlation asset. Chiou, Lee and Chang (2009) highlight that the benefits of diversification are more possible between countries since the correlations of asset returns across countries are lower than within a country, and the volatility of a portfolio's yield can be reduced, without sacrificing its expected return, by investing in overseas assets. Accordingly, Cannon and Hillebrandt (1990) describe a common method of achieving diversification as adding international securities to a domestic portfolio. Thus, ETFs give an efficient way to diversify the portfolio in foreign markets without selecting individual stocks or bonds. Additionally, EFTs cover most major asset classes and sectors, offering a broad selection (Popa, 2017).

Empirical Review

Diversification in South Africa

Using the multidimensional scaling approach with a dataset spanning from February 1965 to January 1980, Van den Honert and Affleck-Graves (1985) investigated international diversification for South African investors. The study revealed that, for diversifiable opportunities, South African investors should look at foreign stock exchanges and soft commodities markets. Similarly, Bhana (1986) investigated the possible benefits for South African investors on international portfolio diversification. The study employed the data from 1969 to 1983 to construct efficient international portfolios. The results indicated the improved risk-return characteristics for South African investors pursuing international diversification from 1963 to 1983. Furthermore, Chinzara and Aziakpono (2009), using the bivariate cointegration and multivariate cointegration, investigated the benefits of international equity diversification for South African long-term investors. The study employed the daily stock market indices for seven world stock markets spanning from 1995 to 2008 and found weak integration of South Africa to the major world markets, suggesting that international portfolio diversification is beneficial for South African investors.

Additionally, Kabundi and Mwamba (2012) employed the genetic algorithm (GA) approach to generate a portfolio of a South African investor seeking to maximise return from investing in international stocks. The study used the dataset from 1 January 2005 to 31 January 2008. It incorporated the quadratic mean-variance (QMV) and quadratic variance minimization (QVM) which are non-linear models and were compared with the GA. The results showed that neither the QMV nor the QVM considers the domestic investors' risk attitude towards investing in foreign equities, and does not provide any international diversification benefits.

Campbell (2008) revealed that art is a good way to diversify investment portfolios, especially during periods of financial crisis. As such, Botha, Snowball and Scott (2016) examined art investment in South Africa using a VAR of the art price index, FTSE All-Share Index, house price index and S.A. government bond index. The study employed quarterly data from 2000Q1 to 2013Q3 and found that the South African art market does not offer the opportunity to diversify portfolios dominated by either property, bonds or shares. Furthermore, Bradfield and Munro (2017) investigated the required number of stocks for adequate portfolio diversification in South Africa and found that more stocks are needed in the South African environment.

ETFs for Diversification

ETFs have been mainly considered as products that offer international diversification benefits. As such, Huang and Lin (2011) investigated whether ETFs provide effective international diversification using the mean-variance approach, the Sharpe index and the value at risk (VaR) model. The findings suggested that ETFs are a reasonable strategy to use for diversification. A study conducted by Kanuri and McLeod (2015) evaluated the performance and diversification benefits of international ETFs for U.S investors during and after the global financial crisis of 2008. The study employed the daily data spanning from January 2008 to June 2013 and revealed that U.S. ETFs outperform all categories of international ETFs during the study period.

Using data from the Asian country ETFs and their MSCI indices, Lee, Hsu and Lee (2016) examined whether trading location affects return co-movements and diversification benefits. The results revealed that the magnitude of return co-movements for the Asian country ETFs is higher than the corresponding MSCI indices. Moreover, Thanakijombat and Kongtoranin (2018) examined the performance and diversification benefits of foreign equity ETFs in emerging markets using 17 foreign-equity ETFs traded in 6 emerging markets. The study employed the International Capital Asset Pricing Model (ICAPM), which considers the traditional Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) principle to international investments. The results revealed that these ETFs are more sensitive to downside risk, indicating their vulnerability to market downturns. Thanakijombat and Kongtoranin (2018) further reveal that ETFs are significantly affected by local market conditions and sentiments, making them ineffective international diversification tools.

Neves, Fernandes and Martins (2019) investigated the benefits of ETFs as an investment vehicle using a nonhierarchical clustering technique, and the findings suggested that ETFs' diversification benefits are limited, particularly in times of market turmoil, indicating the existence of contagion between funds that are indexes. Miralles-

Quirós, Miralles-Quirós and Nogueira (2019) analysed the benefits of adding SDGs exchange-traded funds (ETFs) to a stock-bond portfolio and evaluated the out-of-sample performance of four strategies using the returns and volatility forecasts from a rolling sample approach. The results suggested that investors can obtain benefits from investing in ETFs, which track companies focused on contributing to the SDGs, especially those focused on decent work and economic growth and clear improvements in portfolio performance compared with the initial stock–bond portfolio.

Additionally, Gad and Andrikopoulos (2019) examined the diversification benefits of Shari'ah-compliant equity ETFs in emerging markets and found that the ETFs not only improve the risk-adjusted returns of portfolios but also receive proportionally higher weight during crisis periods. Using a Markov Switching Model (MSVAR) model, Yousefi and Najand (2022) examined the relations between dollar flows of U.S.-listed ETFs with exposure to the U.S., Europe, Asia, and the rest of the world following an emergency like the COVID-19 crisis. The results suggested that investors use ETFs to gain exposure to foreign markets and swiftly adjust their portfolio allocation in response to the change in the number of COVID-19 infected people in every location.

Filippou, Gozluclu and Rozental (2024) investigated ETF arbitrage and international diversification benefits. The study argued that the ETF price discovery mechanism is one of the key channels through which global shocks propagate to local economies, leading to increased return correlation with the U.S. market and limiting the benefits of international diversification. The results suggested that countries with stronger ETF price discovery have higher co-movement with the U.S. market, thus supporting the proposed mechanism.

Summary of Empirical Review

Although past studies confirm the benefits of international diversification for South African investors, they often rely on traditional models and overlook structural changes in global integration. More recent research has questioned the effectiveness of ETFs during periods of market stress, pointing to factors like local market influence and contagion. However, most of these studies focus on developed or emerging markets outside Africa, leaving a gap in understanding the diversification potential of JSE-listed foreign ETFs. Additionally, there is limited empirical work using regime-switching models in this context. Therefore, this study fills that gap by assessing the diversification benefits of foreign equity ETFs listed on the JSE using both Markov Regime-Switching, providing a more comprehensive view of their performance under different market regimes.

Data and Methodology

Data

To achieve the objectives of this study, JSE-listed ETFs which track foreign benchmarks are observed. However, the observation is restricted to foreign ETFs tracking

the equity markets of a single country³, and ETFs listed for more than five years by the end of June 2024. Multi-country ETFs are excluded from this study due to data limitations, specifically the absence of a suitable benchmark to evaluate their performance accurately. Their diverse regional exposures make it difficult to assess their diversification impact on the South African market; thus, the focus is placed on single-country ETFs with precise benchmark alignment. Accordingly, this study surveys 10 JSE-listed foreign equity ETFs in Table 1. The JSE All Share Index, which captures approximately 99% of the companies listed on the JSE’s main board, is a proxy for the South African stock market. In this study, the five-year sample period ranges from 01 July 2019 to 28 June 2024 to adequately capture both market uptrends and downtrends. Daily closing prices and exchange rates are obtained from EquityRT.

Table 1. Sample of JSE-listed Foreign Equity ETFs

JSE Ticker	ETF Name	Benchmark Index	Bilateral Exchange Rate
CSP500	10X S&P 500 ETF	S&P 500 Index	ZAR/USD
ETF500	1invest S&P500 ETF	S&P 500 Index	ZAR/USD
ETF5IT	1invest S&P500 IT ETF	S&P500 Info Tech Index	ZAR/USD
STX500	Satrix S&P 500 ETF	S&P 500 Index	ZAR/USD
STXNDQ	Satrix Nasdaq 100 ETF	Nasdaq 100 Index	ZAR/USD
SYG500	Sygnia Itrix S&P 500 ETF	S&P 500 Index	ZAR/USD
SYGEU	Sygnia EuroStoxx 50 ETF	Euro Stoxx 50 Index	ZAR/EUR
SYGJP	Sygnia MSCI Japan ETF	MSCI Japan Index	ZAR/JPY
SYGUK	Sygnia FTSE 100 ETF	FTSE 100 Index	ZAR/GBP
SYGUS	Sygnia MSCI US ETF	MSCI US Index	ZAR/USD

Empirical Model

Following Thanakijombat and Kongtoranin (2018), the international capital asset pricing model (ICAPM) is employed to assess the diversification properties of ETFs with international benchmarks. Under the assumption of partial market segmentation, the model allows for foreign ETF returns to be dependent on local market conditions and international risk factors as follows:

$$R_t^{ETF} = \alpha + \beta^L R_t^L + \sum_{i=1}^{i=-1} \beta^F R_t^F + \beta^{FX} R_t^{FX} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where R_t^{ETF} represents the ETF’s return on day t , α denotes the constant term, and ε_t represents the error term that is independently and identically distributed. The ETF’s daily return is dependent on (i) the daily return of the local market (R_t^L) proxied by the JSE All Share Index, (ii) the daily return of the foreign benchmark index (R_t^F) and (iii) the daily change in the bilateral exchange rate in which the local currency (South African Rands) is the base currency. According to Thanakijombat and Kongtoranin (2018), the lag and lead terms of the foreign benchmark’s return are used to control for potential non-synchronicity in different markets. In Equation (1), daily returns and changes are computed using the natural logarithm.

³ Single-country foreign ETFs are used because the empirical model relies on bilateral exchange rates.

The limitation of the symmetric ICAPM model specified in Equation (1) is that it fails to account for different market conditions and assumes that the relationships are uniform across market conditions. Equation (1) is estimated using a Markov Regime-Switching approach to account for different market conditions. The Markov Regime-Switching approach introduced by Hamilton (1989) estimates the model's parameters under various market conditions. The Markov Regime-Switching model is well-suited for financial analysis because it captures regime changes like bull and bear markets, allowing parameters to shift over time. Unlike traditional models, it identifies these shifts based on the data, handles nonlinear dynamics, and offers a probabilistic view of market states. As such, the Markov Regime-Switching approach is a popular method for modelling the time-varying dynamics of financial market returns and better captures the risk sensitivities of ETFs (Kunjai, et al., 2021). On this basis, Equation (1) is modified into the following Markov Regime-Switching regression:

$$R_t^{ETF} | s_t = \alpha_{s_t} + \beta_{s_t}^L R_t^L + \sum_{i=1}^{i=-1} \beta_{s_t}^F R_t^F + \beta_{s_t}^{FX} R_t^{FX} + \varepsilon_{s_t} \quad (2)$$

In Equation (2), s_t represents the different market regimes or states. In this study, a two-state regime framework is used, such that, $s_t = 1$ denotes State 1 and $s_t = 2$ denotes State 2. To differentiate between periods of high volatility (that is, bearish market conditions) and periods of low volatility (that is, bullish market conditions), the standard deviations (σ_{s_t}) of each regime is analysed. A lower standard deviation is commensurate with lower levels of volatility and, thus, bullish market conditions. α_{s_t} and β_{s_t} denote the coefficient estimates under the different market regimes.

A first-order Markovian process is used, and, therefore, the probability of being in a specific regime depends on the previous regime such that the transition probabilities are defined as:

$$p_{ij} = P(S_t = i | S_{t-1} = j), \quad i = 1, 2, \quad j = 1, 2 \quad (3)$$

The average duration in a specific regime is equal to:

$$D_{i,j} = \frac{1}{1-p_{i,j}} \quad (4)$$

For robustness checks to determine how negative and positive shocks affect volatility on international ETFs, the study employs the Exponential GARCH or EGARCH (1,1) model developed by Nelson (1991) to capture the leverage effect. The main objective of employing this model is to assess whether international ETFs reduce the volatility of an investment portfolio under bear and bull markets. The EGARCH model has several benefits, such as allowing asymmetric effects between positive and negative shocks on the conditional variance of future observations. Furthermore, the parameters are not restricted as highlighted by Nelson and Cao in 1992. The EGARCH (1,1) model can be estimated as follows:

$$\ln(\sigma_t^2) = \omega + \beta \ln(\sigma_{t-1}^2) + \alpha \left| \frac{\varepsilon_{t-1}}{\sigma_{t-1}} \right| + \gamma \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{t-1}}{\sigma_{t-1}} \right) \quad (5)$$

where ω is the constant term, β captures the persistence, α captures the magnitude, and γ captures the leverage effect. The leverage effect is analysed to determine whether the ETF is affected by negative or positive news. A negative leverage effect (γ) suggest that adverse shocks increase volatility more than positive shocks of the same magnitude and vice versa.

Results and Analysis

Preliminary Analysis

Table 2 summarizes the descriptive statistics for each ETF and their underlying benchmark as well as the local market proxy, the JSE All Share Index. On average, the ETFs generate positive daily returns which exceed the average daily returns of their underlying benchmarks as well as the local market proxy. These mean statistics suggest that foreign equity ETFs tend to outperform their benchmark index and the local market in terms of returns alone. The best-performing ETF is ETF5IT with a daily average return of 0.114%. This may be attributed to the recent innovations in the information technology sector which contributed to the industry's success. However, the high return is commensurate with high risk, as depicted by the standard deviation of 1.688%, which is the highest among the funds. All of the return series do not exhibit normality which is typical of financial returns data (Samunderu and Murahwa, 2021).

Table 3 presents the correlation matrix between the foreign equity ETFs and the local market index. Overall, the returns of the funds exhibit low to moderate positive correlations with the returns of the local market index. In particular, the fund with the highest correlation (0.640) to the JSE All Share Index is the SYGUK index, which tracks the FTSE 100 index that constitutes 100 of the most highly capitalized companies listed on the London Stock Exchange. Nevertheless, the low to moderate correlations between the foreign equity ETFs and the local market suggest that the returns of the funds fluctuate in response to shocks in the local market and vice versa. Therefore, these funds may not provide any diversification benefits for local South African investors. However, further analysis in the form of Markov Regime-Switching analysis is needed as correlation does not imply causation nor does it provide any indication of different market conditions. For completion, the highest correlation (0.954) between the funds is with SYGUS and SYG500, which is expected given that these funds track the same market and are exposed to the same market shocks.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Series	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera	Probability
CSP500	0.075	7.698	-5.737	1.195	0.136	5.825	419.16	0.000
ETF500	0.074	8.083	-9.289	1.238	-0.117	7.975	1290.92	0.000
ETF5IT	0.114	10.685	-11.182	1.688	-0.042	7.069	861.93	0.000
STX500	0.075	7.139	-5.950	1.233	-0.009	5.480	319.99	0.000
STXNDQ	0.097	8.881	-6.092	1.474	0.099	4.966	203.15	0.000
SYG500	0.075	7.532	-5.635	1.223	0.143	6.165	525.72	0.000
SYGEU	0.047	6.321	-9.838	1.277	-0.326	7.793	1217.71	0.000

Series	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera	Probability
SYGJP	0.041	6.549	-7.715	1.139	0.140	6.750	735.86	0.000
SYGUK	0.036	6.490	-10.171	1.180	-0.487	10.469	2952.55	0.000
SYGUS	0.071	7.750	-5.912	1.192	0.018	5.807	410.21	0.000
S&P500	0.049	8.968	-12.765	1.344	-0.845	17.542	11154.14	0.000
S&P500IT	0.091	11.300	-14.983	1.760	-0.398	11.357	3667.52	0.000
NASDAQ100	0.074	9.597	-13.003	1.625	-0.520	9.747	2424.99	0.000
STOXX50	0.027	8.834	-13.241	1.330	-0.942	16.051	9049.24	0.000
MSCIJP	0.017	6.808	-5.200	1.133	0.053	5.611	355.38	0.000
FTSE100	0.007	8.667	-11.512	1.1241	-1.135	18.306	12459.30	0.000
MSCIUS	0.049	8.983	-12.922	1.359	-0.872	17.168	10604.63	0.000
JSEALSI	0.025	7.262	-10.227	1.268	-0.683	11.121	3529.45	0.000

Table 3. Correlation Matrix

Series	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
CSP500 (1)	1.000										
ETF500 (2)	0.822	1.000									
ETF5IT (3)	0.763	0.725	1.000								
STX500 (4)	0.904	0.826	0.777	1.000							
STXNDQ (5)	0.837	0.783	0.834	0.881	1.000						
SYG500 (6)	0.909	0.822	0.755	0.905	0.838	1.000					
SYGEU (7)	0.742	0.677	0.603	0.737	0.651	0.752	1.000				
SYGJP (8)	0.681	0.616	0.510	0.667	0.602	0.702	0.654	1.000			
SYGUK (9)	0.718	0.638	0.531	0.713	0.574	0.732	0.861	0.669	1.000		
SYGUS (10)	0.943	0.850	0.796	0.935	0.882	0.954	0.770	0.694	0.743	1.000	
JSEALSI (11)	0.430	0.370	0.392	0.447	0.392	0.435	0.625	0.365	0.640	0.456	1.000

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is employed to examine the stationarity of the series used to estimate the Markov regressions, and the results are presented in Table 4. For all the series, the significant ADF t-statistics reject the null hypothesis of a unit root in the series and confirm that the series is stationary at levels. Given that all the series are stationary, they are appropriate and can be used in estimating the Markov Regime-Switching models.

Table 4. ADF Unit Root Test Results

Series	ADF t-stat	Series	ADF t-stat
CSP500	-35.637*	SP500	-10.381*
ETF500	-37.830*	SP500IT	-42.783*
ETF5IT	-38.201*	NASDAQ100	-42.371*
STX500	-37.091*	STOXX50	-36.441*
STXNDQ	-36.051*	MSCIJP	-37.460*
SYG500	-37.001*	FTSE100	-36.720*
SYGEU	-23.001*	MSCIUSA	-10.406*

Series	ADF t-stat	Series	ADF t-stat
SYGJP	-36.138*	JSEALSI	-35.295*
SYGUK	-35.918*	ZARUSD	-35.885*
SYGUS	-35.464*	ZAREUR	-36.096*
		ZARJPY	-37.240*
		ZARGBP	-34.656*

Notes: *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at a 1%, 5%, and 10% level of significance, respectively.

Baseline Analysis

Prior to interpreting the output from the Markov Regime-Switching models, it is important to distinguish between the different market regimes. In line with existing literature, the regime-specific standard deviations are used to identify the bull and bear market regimes, as summarized in Table 5, along with the transition probabilities and durations. For each fund, the regime with the higher standard deviation is characterized by higher volatility and, thus, represents the bear market regime. On the contrary, the regime with the lower standard deviation is characterized by lower volatility and represents the bull market regime. Overall, the ETFs exhibit higher probabilities of being in the bull market regime and, therefore, display higher average expected durations in the bull regime. These probabilities suggest that foreign equity ETFs generally experience periods of low volatility relative to periods of high volatility. This finding may be because these foreign equity ETFs track developed markets which are characterized by low financial market volatility relative to emerging markets.

The results of the Markov Regime-Switching estimations are provided in Table 6 with a specific distinction between the bull and bear market regimes. Overall, the funds exhibit significant relationships with foreign market risk factors, including the foreign benchmark's returns and changes in the bilateral exchange rate. This characteristic is essential to provide local investors with exposure to foreign markets and, thus, meet the fund's mandate. In terms of local market conditions, all the surveyed ETFs display positive and significant relationships with the returns of the local market index under bull market regimes. This is also the case under bear markets except for the ETF500 fund which displays no significant relationship with the local market proxy. Together, these findings suggest that local market risk factors influence the returns of ETFs tracking international benchmarks under bull and bear market conditions and, therefore, these funds may not serve as efficient diversification tools except for ETF500 under bear markets. Similar findings are reported by Thanakijssombat and Kongtoranin (2018), who assert that the returns of foreign ETFs are still influenced by market conditions, economic dynamics, and investor sentiment in the local market.

Table 5. Classification of Market Regimes and Transition Probabilities

ETF	Regime 1				Regime 2			
	Std. Dev	Market Classification	$p_{1,1}$	$D_{1,1}$	Std. Dev	Market Classification	$p_{2,2}$	$D_{2,2}$
CSP500	0,324	Bull	0.924	13.169	1,221	Bear	0.922	12.762
ETF500	10,496	Bear	0.589	2.435	0,724	Bull	0.988	80.556
ETF5IT	0,830	Bull	0.938	16.018	5,116	Bear	0.794	4.858
STX500	0,385	Bull	0.935	15.389	1,325	Bear	0.914	11.682
STXNDQ	2,027	Bear	0.883	8.563	0,537	Bull	0.907	10.719
SYG500	4,403	Bear	0.816	5.440	0,626	Bull	0.985	65.652
SYGEU	0,365	Bull	0.985	67.807	1,557	Bear	0.922	12.800
SYGJP	0,639	Bull	0.995	211.879	7,491	Bear	0.850	6.669
SYGUK	0,395	Bull	0.996	232.891	2,299	Bear	0.936	15.597
SYGUS	0,423	Bull	0.955	22.172	1,134	Bear	0.936	15.580

Table 6. Markov Regime-Switching Results

	CSP500	ETF500	ETF5IT	STX500	STXNDQ	SYG500	SYGEU	SYGJP	SYGUK	SYGUS
Bull regime										
α	0.036	0.028	0.029	0.042	0.020	0.031	0.013	0.022	0.014	0.031
R_t^L	0.096*	0.290*	0.137*	0.135*	0.082**	0.278*	0.187*	0.217*	0.244*	0.140*
R_t^F	0.272*	0.196*	0.383*	0.248*	0.372*	0.211*	0.682*	0.456*	0.576*	0.262*
R_{t-1}^F	0.397*	0.376*	0.403*	0.446*	0.471*	0.377*	0.076*	-0.005	0.074*	0.420*
R_{t+1}^F	-0.107*	-0.0163	-0.006	-0.069**	-0.027	-0.014	0.009	0.092*	-0.004	-0.054
R_t^{FX}	0.540*	0.441*	0.475**	0.548*	0.566*	0.426*	0.484*	0.350*	0.442*	0.517*
Bear regime										
α	0.033	0.042	0.015	0.010	0.021	0.036	0.020	0.354	0.032	0.011
R_t^L	0.473*	-0.187	0.815*	0.560*	0.547*	0.511**	0.316*	0.385*	0.439*	0.525*
R_t^F	0.215*	0.759***	0.222*	0.199*	0.282*	0.220***	0.466*	0.161	0.404*	0.193*
R_{t-1}^F	0.325*	0.191	0.342*	0.297*	0.331*	0.310**	0.078***	0.047	0.058	0.304*
R_{t+1}^F	0.015	-0.026	-0.019	-0.008	-0.010	-0.011	0.009	0.266	-0.070	-0.006
R_t^{FX}	0.348**	1.049**	0.486*	0.329*	0.342*	0.245***	0.279*	0.273**	0.438*	0.331*

Notes: *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at a 1%, 5%, and 10% level of significance, respectively.

With the exception of ETF500, the relationship between the fund's returns and the returns of the local market is greater under bear markets as highlighted by the magnitude of the R_t^L coefficients. The influence of local market conditions suggests that the abilities of foreign ETFs to serve as effective diversification tools are weakened. Rather than reducing exposure to domestic risks, these ETFs tend to behave similarly to local assets, particularly during market downturns. This reduces the protective benefits investors expect from international exposure and can result in higher overall portfolio risk during periods of local economic stress. Furthermore, the magnitude of local market returns is generally greater than the foreign market returns under bear markets confirming the dominance of local market conditions in foreign equity ETF returns under bear markets. Therefore, the diversification capabilities of foreign equity ETFs are worsened in bear market regimes except for ETF500. On the contrary, ETF500 is the only fund which

displays diversification benefits, particularly in bear markets where the fund's returns are not influenced by local market conditions.

These findings have important implications for various stakeholders. On average, foreign equity ETFs do not serve as efficient diversification tools because they are influenced by local market conditions under bull and bear market conditions. Therefore, investors seeking international diversification should identify alternative financial instruments which provide efficient international diversification. Notably, ETF500 is the only foreign equity ETF which may provide international diversification in bearish market conditions as the fund is not influenced by the local market. Fund managers of these foreign equity ETFs need to carefully re-design their strategies for achieving international diversification and meeting the mandate of international funds, particularly in bear markets where the effect of local market conditions is exacerbated. In this light, fund owners and sponsors need to evaluate the experience of fund managers with respect to achieving international diversification and the objectives of the fund(s). For regulators and policymakers, it is important to identify the channel(s) through which local market conditions influence international ETF returns in an attempt to mitigate such effects. For academics and researchers, future research into identifying alternative tools for international diversification would be beneficial. Moreover, future research could explore the channel(s) through which local market conditions influence international ETF returns which would assist in policymaking.

Table 7 above represents the estimates of the EGARCH model revealing crucial insights into volatility dynamics and diversification benefits of the foreign ETFs for South African investors seeking global exposure. The EGARCH results reveals that the majority of ETFs such as CPS500, ETF500, STX500, STXNDQ, SYG500, SYGEU, SYGJP, SYGUK, and SYGUS exhibit a significantly negative leverage effect, confirming a bearish classification. Only ETF5IT displays a positive and significant asymmetry term, classifying it as bullish. This asymmetry has major implications for diversification for South African investors who turn to foreign ETFs to hedge against local market volatility or currency depreciation.

The bearish nature of these ETFs suggests that during periods of global market crisis or negative news events, these assets tend to experience increased volatility, limiting their ability to provide consistent diversification benefits when they are most needed. In essence, their risk-reducing potential breaks down during crises, as heightened volatility and increased cross-asset correlations tend to converge across markets, including those perceived as safe havens. Therefore, South African investors who rely heavily on these ETFs to diversify away from domestic risks might find themselves exposed to compounding global shocks, especially in systemic downturns such as the COVID-19 pandemic or geopolitical tensions that simultaneously affect global and local markets. Moreover, the consistently high β coefficients across ETFs, mostly above 0.90, highlight the persistence of volatility, suggesting that volatility shocks in these ETFs tend to be longer. This persistence, combined with their asymmetric reaction to negative news, implies prolonged periods of risk during global downturns. Thus, while these ETFs offer valuable long-term exposure to developed markets, they are less effective as short-term volatility hedges, especially under bearish conditions.

In contrast, the ETF5IT, classified as bullish, shows a positive leverage effect, suggesting that volatility increases more following positive news. The bullish asymmetry observed in ETF5IT suggests that it reacts more strongly to favourable developments, such as economic growth prospects, earnings surprises and factors that often characterise growth-oriented sectors like technology or innovation, which ETF5IT may be exposed to. For South African investors, including a bullish ETF like ETF5IT in their portfolio can serve as a strategic buffer against periods of global distress. While most ETFs in the sample increase downside risk due to their bearish characteristics, ETF5IT may help smooth portfolio returns by contributing positive volatility and potentially positive returns during upward market swings without excessively dragging the portfolio during downturns. This asymmetric response supports a more resilient diversification strategy, especially for investors looking to reduce their exposure to global financial turbulence while still participating in global growth.

Table 7. EGARCH Results

ETF	Mean Equation	Variance Equation				Market Classification
	C	ω	α	γ	β	
CPS500	0.0674	-0.0918***	0.1383***	-0.0894***	0.9482***	Bear
ETF500	0.0781	-0.1143***	0.1712***	-0.0539***	0.9457***	Bear
ETF5IT	0.1415	-0.0417**	0.1936***	0.0352**	0.8953***	Bull
STX500	0.0789	-0.0846***	0.1320***	-0.0499***	0.9516***	Bear
STXNDQ	0.1118	-0.0768***	0.1443***	-0.0363**	0.9512***	Bear
SYG500	0.0774	-0.1236***	0.1902***	-0.0829***	0.9250***	Bear
SYGEU	0.0306	-0.0793***	0.1229***	-0.0872***	0.9615***	Bear
SYGJP	0.0363	-0.0933***	0.1494***	-0.0081*	0.9111***	Bear
SYGUK	0.0087	-0.0914***	0.1323***	-0.0761***	0.9561***	Bear
SYGUS	0.0671	-0.1020***	0.1507***	-0.0814***	0.9445***	Bear

Notes: *, **, *** denote statistical significance at a 1%, 5%, and 10% level of significance, respectively

The Markov Regime-Switching and EGARCH results offer complementary insights into the performance and diversification potential of foreign equity ETFs for South African investors. While the Markov Regime Switching model focuses on return dynamics across bull and bear markets revealing that most ETFs remain significantly influenced by local market conditions especially during bear markets, the EGARCH model highlights asymmetric volatility behavior showing that most ETFs react more strongly to negative shocks increasing risk during crises. Both models suggest that foreign ETFs often fail to deliver effective diversification when it is most needed. Notably, ETF500 stands out in the Markov Switching model as the only fund not influenced by local market returns during bear markets, offering potential diversification benefits. Meanwhile, ETF5IT is the only fund in the EGARCH model showing a bullish asymmetry, implying it responds more to good news than bad which also support diversification. The differing performance of ETF500 and ETF5IT stems from their distinct benchmark compositions and sector focuses. ETF500's broad exposure to large-cap U.S. equities makes it less sensitive to South African market downturns, enhancing its diversification potential during bear markets. In contrast, ETF5IT's concentration in

the technology sector drives a stronger reaction to positive news and growth opportunities, resulting in bullish volatility that supports diversification during market upswings. Overall, while most ETFs fall short as diversification tools in crises, ETF500 and ETF5IT offer unique but limited diversification advantages under specific conditions.

Conclusion

The objective of this study was to investigate whether foreign equity ETFs offer diversification benefits to South African investors under bear and bullish market conditions. To achieve this, a modified version of the International Capital Asset Pricing Model (ICAPM) was employed within a Markov Regime-Switching framework, alongside the EGARCH model, to analyze a sample of foreign equity ETFs listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE). The Markov Regime-Switching results indicate that these ETFs are significantly influenced by local market conditions during both bull and bear markets, thereby limiting their effectiveness as diversification instruments. Complementing this, the EGARCH results reveal that most ETFs exhibit a negative and significant leverage effect, indicating heightened sensitivity to negative shocks and increased volatility during downturns further diminishing their ability to provide downside protection when it is most needed.

However, the study is not without limitations. Firstly, the analysis is restricted to a specific sample of JSE-listed foreign equity ETFs, which may not capture the full spectrum of global diversification instruments available to South African investors. Secondly, the models employed rely on assumptions such as the Markov property in regime switching and the log-linear specification of the EGARCH model that may not fully capture more complex market dynamics or structural breaks. Additionally, macroeconomic and global risk factors were not explicitly modelled, which may have contributed to omitted variable bias.

Despite these limitations, this study represents a significant contribution to the literature by being the first to comprehensively assess the diversification properties of JSE-listed foreign equity ETFs using both regime-switching and asymmetric volatility models. The findings hold important implications for investors who rely on foreign equity ETFs for international exposure, fund managers tasked with meeting diversification mandates, and regulators overseeing the ETF market. Given the observed limitations in diversification benefits, particularly during bearish regimes, these stakeholders should carefully reconsider strategies for achieving effective international diversification.

Recommendations for future research

Future research could explore multi-country or regionally diversified ETFs to assess whether broader exposure improves diversification, especially during market stress. Comparing JSE-listed ETFs with those from other emerging markets could reveal whether the limited diversification observed is context-specific. Incorporating macroeconomic variables such as interest rates, exchange rates, and global risk indicators would enrich the models by capturing external influences. Additionally, comparing active versus passive ETFs may uncover whether active management provides better downside protection. Finally, examining the impact of currency hedging strategies could clarify

whether managing exchange rate risk enhances diversification for South African investors.

Abbreviations

ADF	Augmented Dickey-Fuller (Unit Root Test)
AMH	Adaptive Market Hypothesis
CAPM	Capital Asset Pricing Model
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
EGARCH	Exponential Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity
ETF	Exchange Traded Fund
FTSE	Financial Times Stock Exchange
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GARCH	Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity
ICAPM	International Capital Asset Pricing Model
JSE	Johannesburg Stock Exchange
MSCI	Morgan Stanley Capital International
MSVAR	Markov Switching Vector Autoregressive
NAV	Net Asset Value
QMV	Quadratic Mean-Variance
QVM	Quadratic Variance Minimization
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
STOXX	Stock Index (Euro Stoxx 50)
VAR	Vector Autoregression
VaR	Value at Risk
ZAR	South African Rand

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